

Experiential Learning Applied To The Teaching Of Arithmetic And Geometric Sequences In High Schools

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 01, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: September 01, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Arithmetic Sequence Experiential Learning, Geometric Sequence, Mathematics Achievement, Students' Attitudes</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5363151</p>	<p><i>Experiential learning is one of the educational trends of the twenty-first century that has piqued the interest of educators and policymakers in many countries around the world. Experiential learning is beneficial in education in general and mathematics education in particular because it helps to bear the potential of students' knowledge and skills, as well as positive students' learning attitudes, and because it connects the two aspects of knowledge: theory and practice. The general education program in mathematics was issued in Vietnam in 2018 with views on the content and methods of teaching and learning math, emphasizing the cross-cutting and critical role of experience activities within the framework. The study was conducted to test the effectiveness and feasibility of applying experiential learning in mathematics to participate in learning positively, increase students' motivation and interest in learning, and impact this method for students' math learning results. A series of pedagogical experiments were conducted with 39 grade 11 students on arithmetic and geometric sequences to verify the research objectives. Real-world problems associated with these two topics were given to the students to solve. Through qualitative analysis of classroom observation results and students worksheets, quantitative analysis of pre-test and post-test with SPSS software and opinion survey, the study found a positive impact of these experiential learning activities on math learning attitudes and student achievement progress.</i></p>

Introduction

Learning that is student-centered, experiential, technology-based, and query-based, as well as empathic and understanding, is the educational trend of the twenty-first century (Habib, Nagata & Watanabe, 2021). The content of the general education program promulgated by the Ministry of Education and Training in Vietnam in 2018 mentioned, "The math program focuses on applicability, linking to practice or educational subjects and activities. Many different types of practical and experiential activities in mathematics education reflect this as well, including but not limited to implementing math learning topics and projects, especially topics and projects on the application of mathematics in practice; organize math learning games, math clubs, forums, seminars, math contests. Create opportunities to help students apply their knowledge, skills and experiences into practice in a creative way" (MoET, 2018). As a result, experiential teaching activities create environments where students can learn and be creative while exploring and applying their knowledge and experience to real-world situations (MoET, 2018). Consequently, incorporating experiential learning into teaching mathematics topics is essential for future mathematics education (McCarty, Ford & Ludes, 2018).

Experiential learning has been studied and applied in teaching many mathematical topics at both high school and university levels, such as the equation of a circle (Tong et al., 2019), the angle between two planes and the continuity of functions (Davidovitch, Yavitch & Keller, 2014), mathematics with statistics (Venkatraman, Overmars & Wahr, 2019), arithmetic (Mayoral-Rodríguez, Timoneda-Gallart & Pérez-Álvarez, 2018), some topics Advanced Algebra (Wynn, 2018).

Literature Review

The concept of experiential learning

Many educators have studied experiential learning in a variety of fields. Experiential learning, according to Kolb (1984), is "...the process by which knowledge is created through the transformation of personal experience" (Kolb, 1984; as cited in Cotič et al., 2020; Mutmainah, Rukayah & Indriayu, 2019). The basic experience and the universal experience, according to Dewey (1938), are the two categories in which experience can be divided. Experiences are essentially a collection of random activities or participation in events. On the other hand, universal experience occurs after a disciplined reflective survey process – integrated with prior experience and purposeful consideration of future experiences (Dewey, 1938; as cited in Breunig, 2017). Sharing the same view, Davidovitch, Yavitch and Keller (2014) argue that experiential learning can be divided into two groups: (1) learning through personal experiences in life and events; and (2) learning through designed programs. With

the interpretation in the second group, it is necessary to prepare in advance and go through the whole process to conclude (Davidovitch, Yavitch & Keller, 2014). In this sense, experiential learning is an active learning process mastered by the student through direct participation, supported by experience, analysis, and reflection (Habib, Nagata & Watanabe, 2021; Mutmainah, Rukayah & Indriayu, 2019). Similarly, the author Voukelatou (2019) argues that students play a leading role in the learning process and that the effectiveness of learning depends on the "learning style" and "thinking" of the students (Voukelatou, 2019). In the words of Mutmainah, Rukayah, and Indriayu (2019), experiential learning encourages students to think critically and creatively, investigate, ask questions, make decisions, and apply what they have learned while engaging in activities. Students' acquisition of skills and formation of knowledge is the result of their direct participation in experiences, and these experiences aid in the development of the students' further development (Atherton, 2009; cites Chesimet, Githua & Ng'eno, 2016), focusing on developing students' potential (Mc Pherson-Geyser, de Villiers & Kawai, 2020; Tong et al., 2019).

Features of experiential learning

According to Dewey (1938), authenticity is essential for experiential learning and increases learner motivation (Dewey, 1938; as cited in Cotič et al., 2020), encouraging personal commitment and student persistence in an active learning role (Behrendt & Franklin, 2014). According to Venkatraman, Overmars and Wahr (2019), the factors that bring about the success of the experiential learning framework are that each student must be directly involved in the experience through performing tasks. Each student must transform the experiences gained through analytical skills into higher-order thinking strategies and, ultimately, take rational action in response to any feedback received (Venkatraman, Overmars & Wahr, 2019).

Regarding the relationship between teachers, students, and subject content in experiential learning, Kolb and Kolb (2017) argue that this is the unique point of experiential learning. As a result, the subject is strategically located so that both teachers and students can gain firsthand knowledge of it. Information is transmitted to them, but they also generate it. This method has an equal impact on all relationships, where all subjects can participate in the subject experience to the same extent directly as they can with the previous method. Depending on how the experience is conducted, each individual will have a unique perspective on the subject, and people with varying learning styles will have varying perspectives on the subject as a result (Kolb & Kolb, 2017).

According to Voukelatou (2019), when students participate actively in experiential learning, they do so based on their thoughts, feelings, and openness throughout the educational process. The teacher is a member of the learning team who, in collaboration with the students, creates learning situations that promote experiential learning and assists students in interacting with the learning content in order for them to gain understanding. According to the author, experiential teaching techniques that can help enhance student's active participation, interaction and communication include question-answer, discussion, role-play, case study, model interviews, educational tours, brainstorming, confrontation, expert interviews, exercises, group work, art education and debate (Voukelatou, 2019). This view is similar to Vietnam's General Mathematics Education Program issued in 2018, which clearly states that hands-on activities and experiences in mathematics education can be carried out with a wide range of students, such as: implementing learning topics and projects on Mathematics, especially topics and projects on applying mathematics in practice; organizing math learning games, math clubs, forums, seminars, math contests (MoET, 2018). Research by Davidovitch, Yavich and Keller (2014) introduces the form of "mathematical debate". Accordingly, this is a form of group emulation (each group gives a common solution); students resolve high-level problems and present their solutions in a group, defend and correct their solutions in front of listeners and members of other groups. The most important aspect of emulation is becoming familiar with and commenting on the members' options (Davidovitch, Yavich & Keller, 2014).

Accordingly, experiential learning is closely related to project-based learning (PBL) (Breunig, 2017; Cline et al., 2019; Habib, Nagata & Watanabe, 2021; Larmer, 2015; Scogin et al., 2017; Voukelatou, 2019) and cooperative, collaborative learning (Burrell et al., 2017; Habib, Nagata & Watanabe, 2021; Scogin et al., 2017; Venkatraman, Overmars & Wahr, 2019). Author Larmer (2015) defines project-based learning as experiential activities related to oriented and open-ended problems and questions; real use of content and skills; student-oriented learning; students create productions, presentations, or performances that address problems and guiding questions (Larmer, 2015). Cooperative learning is one of the methods to organize group work to improve learning effectiveness and student achievement through appropriate organization of how students interact with each other and participate in achieving goals together (Zaitou, 2003; as cited in Algani & Alhajja, 2021; Hossain & Airffin, 2017). Due to these characteristics, these learning approaches can create favorable conditions for experiential learning to produce positive outcomes.

Experiential learning cycle

Many studies on the application of experiential learning have been conducted in a variety of educational settings. For mathematics education, research by authors Muro and Terry (2007); Davidovitch, Yavich and Keller (2014); Chesimet, Githua and Ng'eno (2016); Avelino, Ignacio and Joseph, 2017; Mutmainah, Rukayah and Indriayu (2019); Roberts, Breedlove and Strode (2016); Tong et al. (2019); Venkatraman, Overmars and

Wahr (2019) studied the experiential teaching model based on the 4-step model in Kolb (1984). Besides, the study of the authors Kolb (2014); Breunig (2017); Kolb & Kolb (2017); Hsu (2019); Cotič et al. (2020); Lamy, Kawtar, Mohamed and Mohamed (2020); Mc Pherson-Geysler, de Villiers and Kawai (2020) in general education and other fields also mentioned the application of this model. According to Kolb (1984), the four stages of experiential learning include (1) Individual experience, (2) Reflective observation, (3) Abstract conceptualization and (4) Active experimentation (Breunig, 2017; Chesimet, Githua & Ng'eno, 2016; Cotič et al., 2020; Davidovitch, Yavich & Keller, 2014; Kolb, 1984; Kolb, 2014; Kolb & Kolb, 2017; Lamy, Kawtar, Mohamed & Mohamed, 2020; Mc Pherson-Geysler, de Villiers & Kawai, 2020; Muro & Terry, 2007; Mutmainah, Rukayah & Indriayu, 2019; Tong et al., 2019; Venkatraman, Overmars & Wahr, 2019). The above model is described by Chesimet, Githua and Ng'eno (2016) as follows: Students start from an experience that is associated with a certain situation (experience) and then reflects on experiences from many aspects (observation). From those reflections, students form concepts or conclusions and build into theories or models (conceptualization) for them to experiment and act (experiment) (Chesimet, Githua & Ng'eno, 2016). In addition, Kolb (2014) describes the process of learning through and from experience that takes place by (1) engaging in individual experiences with (2) observation and reflection, (3) forming knowledge, and (4) apply and test concepts in new situations (Kolb, 2014). This learning cycle is depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The experiential learning cycle (Kolb, 1984; as cited in Breunig, 2017)

Apart from that, Pfeiffer and Jones (1983) proposed a five-step experiential learning process, including the following steps: the experiential situation, sharing; implementation; generalization; and application. According to this model, active, experiential learning allows students to apply their knowledge in real-world situations while simultaneously developing their skills (Pfeiffer & Jones, 1983; as cited in Davidovitch, Yavich & Keller, 2014).

Advantages of experiential learning

The benefits of experiential learning in education, in general, have been well documented in numerous studies (Breunig, 2017; Habib, Nagata & Watanabe, 2021; Kolb, 2014; Mc Pherson-Geysler, de Villiers & Kawai, 2020; Scogin et al., 2017) and mathematics education in particular (Avelino, Ignacio & Joseph, 2017; Burrell et al., 2017; Chesimet, Githua & Ng'eno, 2016; Davidovitch, Yavich & Keller, 2014; Muro & Terry, 2007; Mutmainah, Rukayah & Indriayu, 2019; Tong et al., 2019; Venkatraman, Overmars & Wahr, 2019; Weibern, Basile & Albright, 2011). In general, experiential learning improves learning quality and effectiveness (Habib, Nagata & Watanabe, 2021; Kolb, 2014; Mayoral-Rodríguez, Timoneda-Gallart & Pérez-Álvarez, 2018; Mc Pherson-Geysler, de Villiers & Kawai, 2020; Scogin et al., 2017; Venkatraman, Overmars & Wahr, 2019; Wynn, 2018), motivating learning (Venkatraman, Overmars & Wahr, 2019; Weibern, Basile & Albright, 2011), developing students' learning styles such as responsibility, self-directed learning, active classroom participation (Breunig, 2017; Mc Pherson-Geysler, de Villiers & Kawai, 2020; Wynn, 2018) and development thinking capacity development (Burrell et al., 2017; Habib, Nagata & Watanabe, 2021; Mayoral-Rodríguez, Timoneda-Gallart & Pérez-Álvarez, 2018; Mutmainah, Rukayah & Indriayu, 2019; Venkatraman, Overmars & Wahr, 2019). Research by the authors Chesimet, Githua and Ng'eno (2016); Tong et al. (2019); Venkatraman, Overmars and Wahr (2019) show the effect of experiential learning on students' mathematical creativity. With a controlled experimental method, the study of Chesimet, Githua and Ng'eno (2016) concluded that the experiential learning method is more effective in enhancing students' mathematical creativity than students' mathematical creativity with traditional teaching and learning methods. As a result, experiential learning allows students to be creative in mathematics by constructing meaning from the knowledge and developing critical thinking about mathematics. According to the authors, students' problem-solving abilities are enhanced through experiential learning (Chesimet, Githua & Ng'eno, 2016). For math problem-solving skills, according to Mwei (2017); Manfreda Kolar and Hodnik (2020), creating conditions for students to solve unfamiliar real-life problems has positive implications for the formation and development of students' mathematical abilities. Research by Davidovitch, Yavich and Keller (2014) shows that experiential activities in mathematics help to improve students' knowledge and understanding of mathematics, active learning activities, and reduce burden curriculum and help students succeed in solving tasks that require a deep understanding of the lesson as well as a willingness to tackle unfamiliar problems (Davidovitch, Yavich & Keller, 2014). Similar results were also

reported by Mayoral-Rodríguez, Timoneda-Gallart and Pérez-Álvarez (2018) in the study on applying experiential learning in teaching Mathematics.

Furthermore, the application of experiential learning has several advantages for teachers. With experiential learning, students develop critical thinking skills and lifelong learning skills, so teachers must consider whether teaching methods are in harmony to teach students skills or not (Wang, 2006). As a result, according to Pittaway and Cope (2007), experiential learning encourages the teaching process to transform from a traditional approach to one that emphasizes practical learning opportunities (Pittaway & Cope, 2007). According to Tong et al. (2019), experiential activities motivate schools and teachers to develop educational programs, create an educational and cultural environment, and build a friendly learning environment (Tong et al., 2019).

Limitations of experiential learning

Although experiential learning has been studied for a long time and its education benefits have been clarified by many studies, its application in teaching practice still has limitations and a certain regime. In the study on applying experiential learning to higher education, Kolb and Kolb (2017) pointed out some difficulties in practical application, which can be related to similar obstacles in education. Experiential learning is being used to teach mathematics at the secondary school level. Accordingly, the authors argue that not viewing experiential learning encompasses all four modes of the learning cycle (see Figure 1) and is applicable in all learning situations in class and life is the source of many difficulties in the practical application of the method. Furthermore, the disparity between theoretical courses and hands-on activities reduces the effectiveness of both types of learning activities simultaneously. Specifically, classroom conceptual reflections and analysis are not integrated with learners' actions to change and improve their conditions in learning projects. The fixed-duration learning system creates the gap, so the teacher mainly focuses on teaching higher-level knowledge, while experiential learning programs are seen as ancillary and only prepare students for low-level professional development (Kolb & Kolb, 2017). In agreement with Kolb and Kolb (2017), authors Cranton (2011) and Tong et al. (2019) also found obstacles in terms of timetable, class structure, and student size to apply experiential learning in teaching (Cranton, 2011). The difficulties are related to the rules, explicit and implicit understanding of curriculum implementation, learning content and textbooks, student participation requirements, grades. The socio-cultural background of students and teachers (Giroux, 2015). Furthermore, the author Darling-Hammond (2016) expressed concern that the assessment method used in the traditional teaching program is incompatible with the learning content and pedagogy of experiential learning, as stated in the article.

Assessment associated with experiential learning

According to Venkatraman, Overmars and Wahr (2019), learning and assessment go hand in hand, so it is necessary first to determine that learning is the basis for assessment to be carried out in an educational setting. In the author's opinion, students concerns about the purpose of an assessment, whether students assess what they learn, and whether or not course experiences should be considered. It is also necessary to consider aspects such as the nature of the assessment, fairness, and the public interest. On the other hand, research shows that assessing students' knowledge and skills must be in harmony with the above aspects (Venkatraman, Overmars & Wahr, 2019). According to the author Payne (1997), the assessment provides an opportunity to integrate cognitive, attitude, and psychological aspects that have been imparted to learners during the teaching process. The cognitive aspects mentioned by the author include knowing, understanding, applying, analyzing, synthesizing, and evaluating (Payne, 1997; as cited in Venkatraman, Overmars & Wahr, 2019).

On the other hand, practical assessments can be made as students participate in active classroom learning activities. Accordingly, there are various approaches to conducting student assessments, ranging from informal to formal. Whatever the assessment method used, teachers must first determine which skills will be assessed to develop an appropriate assessment plan (Venkatraman, Overmars & Wahr, 2019).

Additionally, Kolb and Kolb (2017) built a self-assessment tool called Kolb Educator Role Profile (KERP) to help teachers evaluate their teaching methods from the point of view of the experiential learning cycle. The KERP model describes four teacher roles: Facilitator, Subject Expert, Standard-Setter/Evaluator, and Coach. This model assists teachers in becoming more aware of the types of instruction available, what is required of teachers and students in their respective roles, and making the best decision possible in specific situations. This model is freely accessible at <http://survey.learningfromexperience.com/> (Kolb & Kolb, 2017).

Theoretical framework

Experiential teaching process

The research proposes a process for designing and organizing experiential mathematics education that includes five stages, which are as follows: design, organization, implementation, and evaluation:

Stage 1: Identify the learning topic. Based on the educational objectives, the characteristics of mathematics are determined in the general education curriculum in mathematics, based on each goal identified in each topic, characteristics of students, basic conditions. In each school, teachers identify and build learning topics.

Stage 2: Build the idea of organizing the experience. Based on the identified learning topic and classroom conditions, the teacher chooses an appropriate experiential teaching organization. Teachers can accomplish this by combining a variety of organizational forms in order to increase the efficiency of the teaching process. A

close relationship between objectives, content and the structure and organizing activities must be demonstrated. It is necessary to define goals and methods of implementation for each activity in order for it to be completed successfully.

Stage 3: Prepare learning tools. In this step, the teacher will prepare the necessary equipment and learning tools for the experience session. Teachers train and equip with basic knowledge so that students can apply it in experiential lessons.

Stage 4: Organize experiential activities. From the understanding of related knowledge, new knowledge will be clarified in this stage; students conduct practice and practice experience under teachers' guidance. After the educational process, students consolidate old knowledge, develop skills and capture new knowledge and experiences for themselves.

Stage 5: Check and evaluate the results. Designing appropriate assessment tools and criteria helps teachers know the level of achievement of the set goals in terms of students' qualities and abilities, and at the same time, can evaluate the results of the entire experience process. Teachers can use various assessment methods to determine whether or not the lesson was successful at this stage.

Through the study of experiential learning processes by Kolb (1984), Pfeiffer and Jones (1983), and the studies of educators on applying experiential learning in mathematics, the research proposes organizational processes. The steps of the experiential learning process of students are depicted in Figure 1 as the steps of the organization of experiential activities in mathematics instruction. This procedure is comprised of six steps, which are depicted in Figure 2 as follows:

Figure 2. Experiential teaching process

Step 1: Introduce the experience content. The teacher introduced the lesson by naming it and giving a brief overview of the experience's content.

Step 2: Organize the experience. The teacher will experiment with the students; the teacher will state how to proceed, guide the students to perform, and ask for the experience. Students practice their own experiences, usually working in groups. The teacher will supervise the class, provide assistance as needed, and ensure that all students are actively involved in the learning process.

Step 3: Feedback, share, analyze. The teacher organizes for students to present the results obtained through the practice process. The teacher arranges for groups to come together and share their processes and methods of working. The teacher organizes for students to analyze the obtained results and draw their lessons.

Step 4: Outline the content. Teachers let students relate to their own experiences, list the main points drawn after the process, and conclude. The teacher takes notes on the comments and concludes at the end of the class period.

Step 5: Apply. The teacher assists students in applying what they have learned in class to other contexts. The teacher guides students to identify any behavioral changes that students might make after the experiment and creates additional opportunities to apply or discuss what they have learned with others.

Step 6: Summarize. The teacher comments on the experience and assigns the task to experience at home depending on the lesson's content.

Arithmetic sequence and geometric sequence in the mathematics curriculum

The arithmetic and geometric sequences in the 11th-grade math program are quite close to life and nature. Therefore, it is possible to apply the teaching method through experience in teaching this topic. In addition, the Mathematics General Education Program (2018) in Vietnam emphasizes several requirements for the

organization of practical activities and experiences in teaching the topic of arithmetic and geometric sequences, such as:

Activity 1: Practice applying mathematical knowledge to practice and interdisciplinary topics, such as practicing synthesizing activities related to calculation, measurement, estimation and application of knowledge.

Activity 2: Practice applying mathematical knowledge in population education, for example: applying the addition and multiplier to explain the law of population growth to explain the influence of the population growth to socio-economic progress, explaining the relationship between population growth and ecological environment.

Activity 3: Learn some financial literacy, such as the practice of planning and managing income and accumulating wealth in the short and medium term; identify ways to protect from risk.

Activity 4: Organizing extracurricular activities: math club; math competitions, learning projects, publication of a wall newspaper (or internal magazine) on mathematics, and a club about applying mathematics in computer science and information technology.

Activity 5 (if the school has the conditions to do it): Organize an exchange of good math students in your school and your school, exchange with experts to better understand the role of Mathematics in practice and other fields. (MoET, 2018).

Arithmetic and geometric sequences are necessary for understanding some calculus topics covered in the curriculum, such as exponential and exponential functions. Because of this, it is necessary to improve students' understanding and learning efficiency when it comes to arithmetic and geometric sequences.

Consequently, the study proposes that experiential learning be applied to the topic of arithmetic and geometric sequences to improve teaching quality, spark student interest in learning, and assist students in developing a more positive attitude toward mathematics.

Purpose of the study and research questions that will be addressed

The study was conducted to determine the effectiveness and feasibility of incorporating experiential learning methods into high school teaching arithmetic and geometric sequences. The research will address the following questions:

1. How do students learn the topics of arithmetic and geometric sequences in the Algebra and Calculus 11 textbook?
2. With experiential learning, can students learn more effectively and improve their learning outcomes?
3. How has the student's participation, motivation, and attitude to learning mathematics changed when instructed through experiential learning?

Method

Research on experimental learning on the topic of arithmetic and geometric sequences for a class of 39 students. The researchers conducted an experimental teaching program while conducting classroom observations and analyzing the results of students' group activities on worksheets. Additionally, pre- and post-tests were performed and compared to conclude the student's progress in math learning outcomes. A survey of students' attitudes about experimental lessons was also conducted.

Participants

The experiment was conducted for 39 students of class 11A8 at Luong Dinh Cua High school, O Mon district, Can Tho City, Vietnam. The participants were chosen for their availability and their willingness to participate in the learning process. Besides, this research has also shown no student prejudice or disregard and no adverse impacts on the students.

The researchers created a pre-test and a post-test on an experimental class that they then administered. Using the test results, we conducted a preliminary investigation to determine whether or not the hypotheses were correct. It was determined that designing a pre-test and post-test for a single group would be the most appropriate method of evaluating teaching effectiveness. In their extensive methodological comments on the design of this study, Marsden and Torgerson (2012) provided valuable insight.

Study Design and Instruments

The experimental process was shown in Table 1 below.

Content	Activities
Pre-test	Check the students' ability to solve real-world problems with the content of numbers before experimenting.
Experiment 1: Teaching the definition of arithmetic progression	Implement experiential learning. Record and evaluate group and individual activities. Do reinforcement exercises.
Experiment 2: Teaching the definition of exponentials	Implement experiential learning. Record and evaluate group and individual activities. Do reinforcement exercises.
Post-test	Check the students' ability to resolve real-world problems with the addition and exponential content after the experiment.

Survey on experiential activity lessons	Survey students with an online survey about experiential activity lessons.
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The plan to organize activities in two experimental periods, 1 and 2, was as follows:

Lesson 1: Teaching the definition of the arithmetic sequence

Activity 1: Divide the work and prepare for the lesson. The class was divided into six groups by the teacher, each of which had six or seven students. Each group had a leader and a secretary, and they were expected to collaborate. Each group arranged their seats so that it was convenient for group activities. Also, each group prepared their writing paper and wrote down the information of the whole group on the paper. The teacher distributed study cards and learning tools for the experiential lesson.

Activity 2: Conduct experience according to the requirements of the problem of "building towers". After dividing the groups and preparing the work, the teacher conducted students to practice experiential activities as required by the problem of "building towers". The teacher directly guided, observed and adjusted the practice experience of the groups.

The problem of "building towers":

Question 1: Please arrange the bamboo sticks given into a tower as shown above; how many bamboo sticks are needed?

Question 2: If we build more 4th floor, how many bamboo sticks are needed?

Question 3: Please calculate the number of bamboo sticks on each floor and fill in the corresponding boxes.

Floor	1	2	3	4	5	6	10	20
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Number of bamboo sticks

Question 4: Find the relationship between the number of bamboo sticks on two adjacent floors?

Question 5: Please show me how to calculate the number of bamboo sticks on the 10th and 20th floors. Moreover, the formula for calculating the number of bamboo sticks on any n th floor.

Question 6: If we can build a tower with the number of bamboo sticks on the bottom floor is 51, what is the number of floors?

Activity 3: Feedback, edit and correct the lesson content. The teacher called a group representative to answer the obtained results and another group to comment on the previous group's answers. The teacher makes general comments and gives the results of the math problems for students to record.

Activity 4: Carry out solving exercises using the problem of "elevator escalator". The teacher let the students solve the "rolling elevator" problem and called on group 1 to present the problem results to the whole class. The teacher comments on the solution and corrects the answer to the problem.

Activity 5: Teacher announces homework and ends class.

Lesson 2: Teaching the definition of a geometric sequence

Activity 1: Divide the work and prepare for the lesson. The teacher divided the class into ten groups; each group had 3 or 4 students, each group assigned a leader and a secretary. Let each group arrange their seats so that it was convenient for group activities. Each group prepared their writing paper and wrote down the information of the whole group on the paper. The teacher distributed study cards and learning tools for the experiential lesson.

Activity 2: Conduct the experience required by the problem "Decorate the stupa". After dividing the group and preparing the work, the teacher conducted students to practice experiential activities as required by the "Decorating the stupa" problem. The teacher directly guided, observed and adjusted the experience practice of the groups.

The problem "Decorate the stupa":

It is planned to build a 9-story tower at a certain temple; according to the structure, the floor area of the lower floor is equal to $10/9$ of the floor area of the upper floor, knowing the floor area of the top floor of the tower is $7m \times 7m$. Calculate the floor area on each floor and the number of cement tiles needed to cover the entire tower.

Knowing that the floor tiles used are squares of size 50cm×50cm? (the area of each floor is rounded to 2 decimal places, the number of bricks is rounded up and to the nearest unit).

Question 1: What is the area of each brick?: ... m^2

Question 2: Please fill in the following table:

	Floor	Area	Number of cement tiles
	9	$7m \times 7m =$	m^2
	8		
	7		
	6		
	5		
	4		
	3		
	2		
	1		

Question 3: What do you think about the floor area on two adjacent floors?

Activity 3: Feedback, edit and correct the lesson content. The teacher called a representative of one group to answer the results obtained and two groups to comment on the answers of the previous group. The teacher made general comments and gave the results of the math problems for students to record.

Activity 4: Carry out solving exercises using the problem "Potential investment". The teacher assigned the students to resolve the problem "Potential investment" and called on a group to present the problem results to the whole class. The teacher commented on the solution and corrected the answer to the problem.

Activity 5: The teacher announced homework and ended class.

The pre-test was done in the form of a study sheet. The content of the test was designed to assess students' ability to handle practical problems with the content of the number series (number sequences).

Problem: Rocky intends to overthrow rich guys like Bill Gates or Warren Buffet to become the richest man on the planet. However, instead of writing software like Gates, playing the stock market, or trading real estate like Buffet, Rocky decided to invest in raising rabbits. But not an ordinary rabbit but very special:

Rocky first bought a pair of newborn rabbits as capital,

Rabbits that will never die, male and female,

After two months of being born, each male and female rabbit pair will start having a new pair of baby rabbits., consisting of a male and a female.

Nevertheless, if it is a business, it must be calculated carefully; after n months, it is not known how many pairs of rabbits will be. In general, it is not possible to keep raising and counting until the end of the month; maybe you will lose your capital and then spend it. So Rocky came up with a way to write a computer program to calculate the number of rabbits obtained after n months. To write the software, Rocky needed to calculate some basic rabbit numbers. Please perform the calculation of the following requirements:

a) Calculate the number of pairs of rabbits at months 8, 10, 13, 15.

b) Knowing that the number of pairs of rabbits in each month forms a sequence, create a recursive formula to compute the number of rabbit pairs at any n th month.

After raising rabbits for a while, Rocky began to count the number of rabbits on the farm, with the number of rabbits counted at 2584 pairs; tell me how many months Rocky has been doing the rabbit raising plan?

The following was the content of the post-test when students participated in experiential activities on the topic of arithmetic and geometric sequences.

Problem1: Christmas is an annual festival commemorating the birth of Jesus, celebrated on December 25th as a religious and cultural celebration in many countries around the world. These days, we can see images of Christmas trees in many public places, churches. A car trading company in Can Tho city also plans to erect a Christmas tree to celebrate the holiday. The shop owner decided to recycle used oil bottles to make the pine tree frame to save costs. Knowing that the number of oil tanks on the bottom floor is 41 bottles, the number of oil tanks on the upper floor is less than the lower floor is two oil tanks. Help the shop owner calculate detailed figures to implement the set plan (conventional floor number is marked from the bottom up).

a) Calculate the number of oil tanks in the 1st, 2nd, 3rd, 10.

b) Make a formula to calculate the number of oil tanks on any floor.

c) Know that the number of oil tanks on the top floor is 5. Calculate the number of floors of the pine tree.

d) Calculate the total number of vials required to build the above Christmas tree.

Problem2:Legend has it that one day a mathematician came to the billionaire and offered to "sell" money to him continuously for 30 days in the following way:

Day 1: "sell" 10 million VND for 1 VND

Day 2: "sell" 10 million dong for 2 dong

According to such a rule, each subsequent day will double the "sell" price of the previous day.

Without hesitation, the billionaire immediately agreed, thanking the mathematician for giving him an unbelievable money-making opportunity.

Do the following to check if a mathematician is a "dumb" person?

a) How much money do 11 mathematicians receive the 10th day?

b) Calculate the total amount that the billionaire spent in this transaction.

In this strange "buy-sell", how much money did the billionaire "profit" make?

The student survey was designed based on a Likert scale with five levels: Very Satisfied - Satisfied - Neutral - Unsatisfied - Very Unsatisfied.

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Data collection and analysis

When conducting research, the research team engages in teaching, observing, and gathering information to reflect experiential learning related to the feasibility and effectiveness of the teaching process. Data were collected based on class observations, the pre-test and post-test, and students' survey results. Following that, the statistical method of evaluating students' problem-solving skills is used to analyze and process the experimental data, which results in the evaluation of the findings. The data were analyzed quantitatively (using the SPSS 20 software) and qualitatively (using a qualitative analysis tool).

Results and Discussion

Quantitative results of pre-test and post-tests

Shapiro-Wilk test was performed to check that the point data are normally distributed. The data processing results through SPSS 20 software show Sig values of the two data scores are greater than 0.05, so it can be concluded that the two test scores data before and after the experiment are normally distributed (see Table 2).

Table 2. Shapiro-Wilk normal distribution test results

	Shapiro-Wilk	
	Statistic	Sig.
Pre-test	0.966	0.278
Post-test	0.951	0.089

When we were finished developing the lesson plan, we conducted a quantitative analysis of the scores obtained by students on their examinations both before and after the experiment. Table 3 shows the experiment results, which allow us to assess the effectiveness of the lesson by comparing the results of the examinations taken before and after the experiment.

Table 3.Score distribution table before and after the experiment

Scores	Pre-test	Post-test
0	0	0
1	0	0
2	1	0
3	1	1
4	6	1
5	7	7
6	6	5
7	11	8

The study looks at the difference between the mean values of the two tests to determine the effectiveness of pedagogical effects on students' mathematics performance. Verification is performed by paired sample test through SPSS software. The results of data processing are shown in Tables 4, 5 and 6.

Table 4. Paired samples statistics

	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pre-test	6.08	39	1.753	0.281
Post-test	7.10	39	1.774	0.284

Table 5. Paired samples correlations

	N	Correlation	Sig.
Pre-test & Post-test	39	0.717	0.000

Table 6. Paired samples test

	Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
				Lower	Upper			
Pre-test Post-test	-1.026	1.328	0.213	-1.456	-0.595	-4.825	38	0.000

Based on the significance level of 0.05 and degrees of freedom of 38, the Sig. (2-tailed) the critical value is equal to $0.000 < 0.05$, and the mean deviation between the pre-test and the post-test is negative. In conclusion, there is a significant difference between the mean scores of the two tests; additionally, the mean score of the post-test is greater than the mean score of the pre-test. Besides, the value of influence level ES (Cohen, Manion & Morrison, 2005) is 0.58, showing that the level of influence is average; this result is consistent with the expectation of the research group due to the time of organization. The experiment was over in a short amount of time. The study concluded that applying teaching methods through experiential activities helped students make progress in math learning results.

Results of experimental lessons

After conducting pedagogical experiments through professional exchange, after-hours attendance and experience gathering, the study found that students were enthusiastic about learning and participating in active group activities. The practical problems and simulations had created excitement and aroused curiosity in mathematics for students. They realized that mathematics was always associated with practice and that practical problems were extremely diverse and lively.

In order for the results of the experimental pedagogical evaluation to be favorable and the results obtained to be highly convincing, the study was conducted to develop qualitative evaluation criteria as follows:

- (1) Ability to collect and process information about the problem of arithmetic and geometric sequences.
- (2) Students' creativity and cooperation in group activities during experiential practice.
- (3) Cognitive ability of students: demonstrated at the level of monitoring and analyzing the experience problem, analyzing the data collected from the problem to complete the learning task, the ability to generalize the problem, state the content and indicate the nature of the knowledge formed.
- (4) Students' interest in similar experiential learning activities.

Through 2 experimental lessons and results from the actual happenings of the class, worksheets, surveys, tests, the following conclusions are made:

- Lesson period 1: teaching the definition of an arithmetic sequence.

In the experimental lesson of addition, students had good cooperation among group members, good division of work in groups. The content of the exercise was analyzed and agreed upon by the members of the group (see Figure 3). It shows that the proposed learning activities helped students increase creativity, show cooperation in group activities, and improve information gathering and processing activities for math problems.

Nhóm 2
 - Ngô Lan Anh
 Lê Yên Quỳnh (Thư thư)
 Võ Minh Đức
 Huỳnh Trần Khánh Toàn
 Võ Ngọc Gia Hưng (Nhóm trưởng)
 Võ Ngọc Gia Huy
 Bùi Trang Nhân
 Trần Yến Nhi

Câu 1: Có 21 que tre để xếp thành 1 tháp 3 tầng.
 Câu 2: Cần 36 que tre để xây thêm tầng để xây được 1 tháp với số que tre tăng đều cũng là 51 que tre thì số tầng của tháp là 13 (tầng)
 Câu 4: 2 tầng liên tiếp nhau chênh lệch nhau 4 que tre.
 Câu 5: CTQ: $U_n = 4n - 1$
 Câu 6: $51 = 4n - 1$
 $\Rightarrow n = 13$ (tầng)
 Vậy số tầng ta xây được với 51 que là 13 tầng ở tầng cuối

Tầng	1	2	3	4	5	6	10	20
Số que tre	3	7	11	15	19	23	39	79

Figure 3. Group 2 solving the problem of "building towers"

During the test, students had difficulty in determining the formula for the number of bamboo sticks on any floor. The teacher proposed open questions for students, like: "How many bamboo sticks are on each floor of the tower?", "given the number of floors n , how will the number of bamboo sticks on the 2nd and third floors be represented? ".

The teacher called group 2 to present their answers and gave group 4 comments on the results. The teacher concluded the answer to the problem and defined the arithmetic progression. The teacher gave examples of an arithmetic sequence and special cases, such as the common difference of zero, which was negative. The teacher gave an arithmetic sequence's general term formula and proved that a number sequence was an additive number. During the lesson, group activities took place enthusiastically under the cooperation of all group members, and the students fully presented the results of the problem and the lesson's content. Thereby showing the students'

interest and excitement in experiential activities and students' awareness was also improved, knowledge was formed in each student through that practice activity (see Figure 4).

Figure 4. The students solving the problem of "building towers"

After the lesson, the study drew some conclusions as follows:

(1) For teachers: fully implement the lecture's content, guide the solution for students, divide groups, divide work, manage the class, meet the requirements of the experiential lesson. The experimental time was just enough in a teaching period, according to the set schedule;

(2) For students: Students cooperate well in activities given by teachers, active group activities. Students took full notes of the lesson content during the lesson.

- Lesson 2: teaching the definition of a geometric sequence.

In the exponential lesson, there was clear coordination and division of work among group members, each member of each group could grasp the requirements of the problem, present, analyze and state the problem. Students' ability to collect and process information about problems and creativity and cooperation in group activities improved through the proposed learning activities.

a. Diện tích mỗi viên gạch là: $0,25 m^2$

b. Hãy điền vào bảng sau:

	Tầng	Diện tích	Số gạch bông
	9	$7m \times 7m = 49 m^2$	196
	8	$49 \cdot \frac{10}{9} = 54,44m^2$	217,76
	7	$54,44 \cdot \frac{10}{9} \approx 60,49m^2$	241,96
	6	$60,49 \cdot \frac{10}{9} \approx 67,21m^2$	268,48
	5	$67,21 \cdot \frac{10}{9} = 74,68m^2$	298,72
	4	$74,68 \cdot \frac{10}{9} = 82,96m^2$	331,84
	3	$82,96 \cdot \frac{10}{9} = 92,18m^2$	368,72
	2	$92,18 \cdot \frac{10}{9} = 102,42m^2$	409,68
	1	$102,42 \cdot \frac{10}{9} = 113,8m^2$	455,2

c. Em có nhận xét gì về diện tích mặt sàn ~~ở hai tầng kế nhau?~~
 Diện tích tổng dần tăng dưới lên không tăng nên $= \frac{10}{9}$

Figure 5. Group 5 solving the problem "Decorate the stupa"

During group work, students had difficulty in calculating the floor area on each floor. The teacher suggested to groups of students with open-ended questions such as: "The area of the 8th floor is 10/9 more than the area of the 9th floor, what math do we perform?", "If the formula calculates the floor area, Can you use the same formula for the number of floor tiles you just calculated?,"...The teacher called a representative of group 5 to answer the results obtained (see Figure 5), then called group 7 and group 2 to comment on the results. The teacher concluded the answer to the problem and defined the exponent. The teacher gave examples of

exponential levels and special cases such as multiples equal to 0 and common multiples equal to 1. Besides, the teacher gave formulas for general terms of an exponential and methods to prove a series of numbers was the multiplier.

During the lesson, all group members cooperated and worked seriously and enthusiastically, and the results of the problem and the lesson's content were fully and presented by the students. Thereby, the proposed learning activities had helped students increase their interest in learning, and new knowledge was also formed in each student through that hands-on experience (see Figure 6).

Figure 6. The students solving algebraic problems

After the lesson, the study drew some conclusions as follows:

- (1) For teachers: fully implement the content of the lecture, guide students to solve, divide groups, divide work, manage classes, meet the requirements of an experiential lesson. The experimental time was just enough in a teaching period, according to the set schedule;
- (2) For students: Students cooperated well in activities given by teachers, active group activities. Students took full notes of the lesson content during the lesson.

Qualitative results related to pre-test

The following were the findings of the qualitative analysis of the students' work completed during the pre-test period. The majority of students could complete it using drawing methods (see Figure 7). Nonetheless, after observing the test-taking process, it became clear that some students were still perplexed about this question.

Figure 7. Pre-test – question a – Students 15, 18

Question b revealed that the students could not distinguish between the recursive and general formulas (see Figure 8). Some students did not list the first terms of the sequence or did not write the condition of n , which was among the mistakes.

Figure 8. Problem 1 – question b – Students 18, 34

For the most part, students struggled when attempting to formulate a general formula for question c. On the other hand, some students (see Figure 9).

<p>c) Taw: $\frac{1}{\sqrt{5}} \cdot \frac{(1+\sqrt{5})^x - (1-\sqrt{5})^x}{2}$ HS 24 (Giả sử là số tháng Rocky thực hiện kế hoạch mua thẻ) $\Rightarrow x = 18$ tháng.</p>	<p>HS 3 c) Rocky đếm được 2584 cặp thẻ nên có thể suy ra Rocky đã thực hiện kế hoạch mua thẻ được 18 tháng. (Theo a)</p>
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Figure 9. Problem 1 – question c – Students 3, 24

Through the test results, it can be seen that most of the students still had difficulty in processing the data on the topic. Numerous students were perplexed by the concepts and definitions of the number series contained within it. Furthermore, the calculation was still done simultaneously, demonstrating a lack of initiative to simplify the problem. On the other hand, some students demonstrated their ability to think critically, be creative, and complete the test.

Qualitative results associated with post-test

According to the results, the student's ability to deal with real-world problems significantly improved in the post-test. With lessons 1a, 1b, the students recognized the additive level pattern and applied the formula to the problem (see Figure 10).

<p>① a) Taw: $u_1 = 41$ $d = -2$ Số bình nhất ở tầng 1, 2, 3, 10 tầng lầu là $u_1 = 41$ $u_2 = u_1 + d = 41 - 2 = 39$ $u_3 = u_2 + d = 39 - 2 = 37$ $u_{10} = u_1 + (n-1)d = 41 + 9(-2) = 23$</p>	<p>HS 39</p>
<p>HS 33 b) Vì số bình nhất ở tầng trên ít hơn tầng dưới 2 bình nhất nên: $u_n = 41 + (n-1)(-2)$</p>	

Figure 10. Problem 2 – lesson 1a, 1b – Students 39, 33

With lessons 1c and 1d, students had memorized and applied the formulas related to the additional level to deal with the requirements of the problem (see Figure 11).

<p>c. Số bình nhất ở tầng trên cùng là 5 $\Rightarrow u_n = 5$ $u_n = u_1 + (n-1)d$ $5 = 41 + (n-1)(-2)$ $\rightarrow n = 19$ Vậy cây thông có 19 tầng. d. $S_{19} = u_1 \cdot n + \frac{n(n-1)d}{2}$ $= 41 \cdot 19 + \frac{19 \cdot 18 \cdot (-2)}{2} = 457$ Vậy tổng số bình nhất cần có để xây dựng cây thông Noel trên là 457 bình nhất.</p>	<p>HS 5</p>
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Figure 11. Problem 2– lesson 1c, 1d – Student 5

In lesson 2a, the students also realized that this pattern formed an exponential (Figure 12).

HS 15

Câu a) $u_1 = 1$; $q = 2$
 Khi mỗi ngày tiếp theo sẽ có giá bán gấp đôi ngày trước đó \Rightarrow đây là dạng tiến cấp số nhân.
 Áp dụng công thức $u_n = u_1 \cdot q^{n-1}$
 $\Rightarrow u_{10} = u_1 \cdot q^{10-1} = 1 \cdot (2)^9 = 512$
 $u_{11} = u_1 \cdot q^{11-1} = 1 \cdot (2)^{10} = 1024$
 Vậy trong ngày thứ 10 nhà toán học nhận được 512 đồng, ngày thứ 11 nhà toán học nhận được 1024 đồng.

Figure 12. Practice test number 2 – lesson 2a – Student 15

In Figure 13, for questions 2b and 2c, students could apply the formula to sum the exponential's first n terms and solve the required problem.

HS 31

b) $S_{30} = \frac{1 \cdot (1 - 2^{30})}{1 - 2} = 1073741823$
 c) Tổng số tiền của toán học trong 30 ngày bán 10 triệu là: $30 \cdot 10 \text{ triệu} = 300 \text{ triệu}$
 Ta có $300 \text{ triệu} - 1073741823 = -773741823$
 Vậy trong cuộc mua bán sẽ phải lỗ 773741823

Figure 13. Problem 2– lesson 2b, 2c – Student 31

Through Problem 2, the research team found that the students could apply the lesson content to solve real-world problems. This result proves that the experiential learning approach helped students form mathematical knowledge more firmly, deeply, remember better, and apply that knowledge to address real-world problems.

Results of a survey of student attitudes

The results of an attitude survey were collected from 39 students in class 11A8 after the class was taught. The questions were evaluated in five levels to determine whether or not the students were interested in the organized teaching method and whether they could acquire knowledge through that activity. Table 7 contains the results of the survey.

Table 7. Student attitude survey results

Questions	Contents	Levels				
		Very Satisfied (%)	Satisfied (%)	Neutral (%)	Unsatisfied (%)	Very Unsatisfied (%)
1	Were the activities organized in the last class exciting for you?	23	41	28	8	0
2	The requirements and activities given in the lesson are suitable for your ability to solve?	20	46	26	8	0
3	Do you find the lesson content easy to understand and close to reality?	18	46	31	2	3
4	Can you learn new knowledge through activities in class?	26	44	28	2	0

5	Activities that help you practice necessary skills (teamwork, thinking, problem-solving)?	28	46	18	5	3
6	Would you like to continue taking classes with the same activities and teaching methods?	33	41	20	3	3

Through the survey results of questions 1 and 6, most of the students in the experimental class liked the learning method based on the activities organized by the teacher during the lesson. The students become more engaged when they participate in experiential lessons. The students took an active role in predicting outcomes, thinking through problems, and analyzing results before drawing on their previous experiences and gaining knowledge. This outcome was reflected in the number of students who felt very satisfied and satisfied with the organized learning activities that had created students' interest in learning math, accounting for 64% of the class. It was found that 74 percent of students were extremely satisfied or satisfied with their experience in classes that included educational activities.

Through question 2, the majority of students thought that the learning situations implemented in the lesson were suitable for their learning ability, in which a total of 66% of students felt very satisfied and satisfied with the difficulty of the problem. In question 3, 64% of students thought that the lesson was easier to understand and closer to reality when it was learned with participating in learning activities. Most of the students stated that the questions of the activities in the class were suitable for themselves, but there were still a few cases where the group did not fully complete the requirements of the problem. The study made some comments to explain the above cases: The division of groups had an unequal distribution of levels between groups, students did not understand the requirements of the problem, students did not know the requirements of the problem. They answered, "I am familiar with this way of learning, so I am still confused, waiting for the teacher to provide the formula".

Survey results of questions 4 and 5 had more than 70% of students think they could learn through experimental lessons and practice necessary skills in the learning process. Students learn, discover, and solve problems independently due to completing math problems set out by teachers, resulting in increased confidence in their math abilities. Aside from that, students practiced necessary skills such as teamwork skills, information search skills, information analysis and exchange abilities, and mathematical communication capacities, among other things.

Conclusion

After the experiment, the research has obtained results consistent with the set objectives. In terms of knowledge, with significance level sig. equal to 0.000, t-test paired test scores before and after the experiment showed the students' math learning results. This outcome is consistent with the authors' research findings and opinions (Mayoral-Rodríguez; Timoneda-Gallart & Pérez-Álvarez, 2018; Tong et al., 2019; Venkatraman, Overmars & Wahr, 2019; Wynn, 2018). Additionally, the average level of influence shows that the designed and conducted experiential activities significantly impacted the knowledge formation, understanding and ability to apply the students' knowledge on arithmetic and geometric sequences. Because the experimental period was not sufficiently long, the researchers hypothesized that students did not adapt well to the new learning method, which helped explain the average influence of the effect. Although the impact was not too large, this was a positive sign of the effect of experiential learning on student achievement in math. In terms of skills, through the analysis of study worksheets and tests, the study found that students made progress in analyzing practical problems, applying learned knowledge to cope with practical problems and computational skills (Davidovitch, Yavich & Keller, 2014; Mayoral-Rodríguez, Timoneda-Gallart & Pérez-Alvarez, 2018). Accordingly, the results of classroom observation during experiential activities show that these activities increased students' interest and motivation to learn and actively engage students' learning activities through doing activities of group work, as well as training students in the skills of assigning tasks, discussing and reaching consensus while working in groups (Breunig, 2017; McPherson-Geyser, de Villiers & Kawai, 2020; Venkatraman, Overmars & Wahr, 2019; Weibern, Basile & Albright, 2011; Wynn, 2018). Besides, the student survey results also show that students had a positive attitude towards experiential activities in mathematics. Students' responses to survey questions show that students were aware of the effectiveness of experiential activities on knowledge formation, the ability to relate learned knowledge to real-world problems. At the same time, students saw their progress in mathematical thinking and practical problem-solving. This outcome provided valuable feedback from the students' perspective. This feedback demonstrates that students had faith in the effectiveness of this new learning method, which encouraged them to actively participate in future experiential learning activities in order to gain

more knowledge. This outcome also explains why many students expressed an interest in learning with this method in future lessons.

Aside from the findings, there are some limitations to the research. In terms of experimental time, the study experimented in a rather short period, and the arrangement of activities took place within the limited duration of the learning program. Due to this limitation, some students have not yet adapted to how activities are carried out, which causes initial confusion. As a result of this, a portion of these students' learning outcomes is negatively influenced. Many other studies have identified that difficulty is also present here (Cranton, 2011; Kolb & Kolb, 2017; Tong et al., 2019).

Based on the findings and limitations of this study, the authors believe that future studies should consider organizing experiential learning in mathematics for a long time, in conjunction with organizing activities inside and outside the classroom or in an interdisciplinary direction. Within mathematics, research can be carried out on various mathematical topics in algebra, calculus, geometry, arithmetic at different levels of study. Furthermore, the combination of experiential learning with problem-based learning and project learning from both a theoretical and a practical perspective can be used to great effect in educational settings. Besides, with the development of science and technology today, integrating technology elements in teaching is also a trend that needs attention (Tran, Nguyen & Trinh, 2020).

Moreover, to enhance the effectiveness of applying experiential learning in teaching mathematics in particular and education in general, studies on improving teachers' understanding in theory and practice of this learning method are unnecessary. Similar to this point of view, the research of Jay and Miller (2016) presents three models of teacher training programs that facilitate learners to be fostered in the theory and practice of experiential learning. The authors identify the main generalizable elements from learning these programs, identify the factors that lead to the separation between theory and practice, and propose more sustainable models (Jay & Miller, 2016).

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